

PSYCHOPHYSIOLOGICAL FEATURES OF ADOLESCENT DEVELOPMENT**Kenjaeva Dilnoza Sadirdinovna**

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Abstract. *The article reveals the psychophysiological features of adolescent development. It is shown that the crisis is associated with the spiritual growth of the teenager, as well as changes in his psyche. It is analyzed that the natural needs of personality development are affected. Reveals susceptibility to external influences, his moral character.*

Keywords: *psychophysiological, crisis, spiritual growth, personality, development, need, morality, image, social, teenager, adolescence.*

ПСИХОФИЗИОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ РАЗВИТИЯ ПОДРОСТКОВ.

Аннотация. *В статье раскрываются психофизиологические особенности развития подростков. Показано, что кризис связан с духовным ростом подростка, а также изменениями в его психике. Проанализировано, что затрагиваются естественные потребности развития личности. Выявляется восприимчивость к внешним воздействиям, его нравственный облик.*

Ключевые слова: *психофизиологический, кризис, духовный рост, личность, развитие, потребность, мораль, образ, социальный, подросток, подростковый возраст.*

INTRODUCTION

As a result of the development of society, people's life activities expand, their intellectual intellect is enriched. Consequently, their philosophical worldview also becomes an important factor in the development of society as a reflection of the historical period. For this reason, different periods of human development lead to the emergence of different forms of philosophy.

In recent years, a number of measures have been taken in Uzbekistan to create psychological services in the field of production, medicine and pedagogy. The issue of ensuring the effectiveness of economic and social reforms in our country, the use of the human factor in production and at all stages of public life, the full realization of the potential of each social person has placed responsibility for the following tasks on psychologists in Uzbekistan. related to psychological services.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

Teenagers try to behave like adults. They tend to demonstrate their abilities, skills and capabilities to their peers and teachers to varying degrees.

This state can be easily seen by simple observation. During this period, teenagers may also become interested in smoking and drinking alcohol. The teenager feels uncomfortable in new roles, such as an adult, a smoker, a drinker.

Teenagers, who are close to children in mental development, but close to adults in needs, experience many uncomfortable and anxious situations that lead to a crisis of the teenager. This crisis is associated with the spiritual growth of the teenager, as well as changes in his psyche.

During this period, the social status of the child changes, new relationships with his relatives, friends, peers arise.

But the biggest changes occur in his inner world. Many teenagers are dissatisfied with themselves. The teenager is also nervous about the fact that his current thoughts about himself do not correspond to the changes happening in him today. This can cause negative thoughts and fear in the teenager. Some teenagers are worried about the fact that they cannot understand why they rebel against others, adults and even their parents. This situation makes them nervous inside and a teenage crisis occurs. The crisis manifests itself in the child's existing depression, desire for solitude, passivity or, on the contrary, stubbornness, obstinacy, aggressiveness, negative attitude to life. At such moments, he experiences a great need to communicate with his friend, who, like him, undergoes great physiological and psychological changes. Whether the friend will have a positive influence on the teenager or a bad one, leading him astray, depends on his moral character.

Under the influence of peers, a teenager can satisfy his needs and desires. If satisfaction brings him great pleasure, then in such cases his casual interest in some action or activity can first develop into a passion, and then into a passion or habit. In this way, students develop a passion for, for example, mathematics, physics or chemistry, carpentry, metalwork or some other work, but in the same way, students can get used to lying, hooliganism and other immoral behavior.

All inadequate behavior in adolescence is caused by too many fleeting desires and too superficial a view of the consequences that follow from them. Almost all harmful desires begin with recreational activities that at first glance seem harmless and easy to fulfill. However, in reality, adolescents are not capable of such things. This is influenced by the natural needs of individual development. If adolescents did only what they could, they would not be able to develop their extrasensory abilities. Teenagers

do not see anything except the immediate satisfaction of their various desires, and they may not be able to stop themselves in time when such desires lead to dangerous consequences. Students' own behavior.

The main task of teachers is to teach them to foresee the consequences of their actions and be able to restrain themselves.

Teenagers are overly enthusiastic and carefree, idleness is very difficult for them, they quickly get tired of monotonous work, lose interest in monotonous work, which greatly affects the success of their educational process. Therefore, it is extremely important to interest them in various types of activities and involve them in various useful activities, as well as involve them in more complex, but opportunity-expanding work for the successful education and upbringing of teenagers. "The essence of adolescence is that the teenager is placed in a somewhat more active social environment, breaks old relationships that developed in childhood, and begins to fight for this environment." Every teenager strives to confirm his identity among the people around him through successful work. Adults should help adolescents succeed in meaningful group activities and allow them to express their values.

Otherwise, they may think highly of themselves and be arrogant. They may do this through negative actions and behavior in response to the fact that their dignity is not recognized and humiliated. Adolescents are extremely imitative; they do not yet have a clear idea and worldview.

They are very sensitive to external influences and emotions. They are also characterized by courage, bravery, and tact. Susceptibility to external influences forces the adolescent to form a personal opinion, but this personal opinion is often unfounded. That is why they try to convey their thoughts despite the guidance of parents, elders, and teachers. Adolescents still lack such mental qualities as prudence, thrift, calculation, and foresight. In a group of peers, as well as classmates, the adolescent is distinguished by compliance. Being dependent and dependent on his group, the adolescent is ready to agree with the general opinion of this group and always follow its decision.

The group often helps to form a sense of "we" in the teenager and strengthens his inner state.

The choice of friends is very important for the teenager. Friendship is very valuable in adolescence. Friends constantly feel the need to be close in spirit and heart. This need manifests itself when teenage friends try to ask how they are doing, to see each other (shake hands and hug), try to sit together and walk together. Many of these very close relationships in the formation of the teenager as a person are of a cooperative nature.

traces of his actions remain in the heart and memory of a person for life.

The behavior and activities of teenagers sometimes reveal contradictions that are beyond their control. The main contradiction is the contradiction between physical, spiritual and material needs, which give rise to many desires, and the rapidly increasing physical, spiritual and material needs, which are extremely limited and in many ways insufficient to not only be forced to satisfy them. emphasized the rest, but at the same time caused a situation of inability to adequately assess this feeling brings This, in turn, causes such behavioral symptoms as rudeness and aggressiveness towards adults, as well as disobedience to the advice and demands of parents and teachers.

The study "Problems of the Sixth Grade" showed an increase in problems associated with the behavioral characteristics of children of this age, and a decrease in academic performance in various subjects as follows: Sixth-graders are 6 times more stubborn than fourth-graders, 10 times more resistant to teachers show, 7 times more often interfere with the will of others, 9 times more often notice other people's shortcomings, 5. It was found that they were 42 times more likely to obey only their own desires and 42 times more often had no motivation for their behavior. (Krakowski A.P. 1970)

Adolescence is often characterized by such negative characteristics as reluctance, stubbornness, obstinacy, failure to recognize one's own shortcomings, belligerence. During this period, teenagers may also become interested in smoking and drinking alcohol. The teenager feels uncomfortable in new roles such as an adult, a smoker, a drinker.

CONCLUSION

Many teenagers are dissatisfied with themselves. Also, the fact that their current thoughts about themselves do not correspond to the changes that are happening in them today makes the teenager nervous, they have many uncomfortable and anxious situations. This can cause negative thoughts and fear in the teenager. Some teenagers are worried about the fact that they cannot understand why people around them, adults and even their parents, are against them. This situation makes them nervous inside and a teenage crisis occurs. The crisis manifests itself as depression in the child, a desire for loneliness, passivity or, conversely, stubbornness, obstinacy, aggressiveness, the emergence of a negative attitude towards life. This crisis is associated with the spiritual growth of the teenager, as well as changes in his psyche. At such moments, he is with his friend, who, like himself, undergoes great physiological and psychological changes.

feels a great need for communication. His moral character determines whether the friend will influence the teenager positively or lead him astray and become a bad influence.

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